

Report on 2021 plant pest survey activities

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At the request of the European Commission, EFSA was asked to support the EU Member States in the preparation and planning of the surveys of the EU quarantine pests (EFSA mandates on plant pest surveillance M-2017-0137 and M-2020-0114).

In response, EFSA developed a toolkit that consists of three pest-specific guidelines, pest survey cards on quarantine and non-quarantine organisms, as well as general survey guidelines and statistical tools (i.e. RiBESS+). The aim of the pest survey cards is to guide the EU Member States in the preparation of plant pest surveys by providing relevant information on the pests for this activity. The aim of the guidelines is to assist the EU Member States in the design of statistically sound and risk-based surveys for quarantine pests.

The purpose of the current document is to facilitate the access to the outputs delivered in 2021 in the context of both mentioned mandates. The listed outputs are delivered in different formats and platforms: as PDF files in the EFSA Journal, as ESRI ArcGIS StoryMaps in EFSA Plant Pest Survey Cards Gallery, videos in the EFSA YouTube Channel and shared presentations at different forums, webinars and online courses. Activities in 2021 focused on mandate M-2021-0014. The activities of 2022-2027 will be focused on the delivery of (i) pest survey cards for all the Union quarantine pests, protected zone pests and provisional quarantine pests; (ii) an expert system tailored to plant health for guiding the users through the survey design (replacement of RiBESS+), and, (iii) optimising multi-pest surveys at crop level for citrus, potato and broadleaved trees pests.

Within the PLANTS Unit, Plant Health Monitoring team (formerly ALPHA Unit, Plant Health team), the following persons contributed to the preparation and delivery of the outputs: Melanie Camilleri, Alice Delbianco, Ignazio Graziosi, Giulia Mattion, Luka Mustapic, and Sybren Vos.

All outputs of the EFSA Pest Survey toolkit can be accessed through the [Index](#) (which was viewed more than 2,000 times), while Pest Survey Cards can be accessed in the [Gallery](#) as well (which was viewed for about 23,000 times) (March 02, 2022). EFSA Surveillance outputs were promoted through the EFSA Plant Health team Twitter account (@Plants_EFSA, 3420 followers on March 02, 2022), gaining an average of about 3000 visualizations per Tweet.

Table 1 shows the outputs published in 2021.

Table 2 shows the events which the Plant Health Monitoring team has organised or collaborated with in 2021.

Suggested citation: Mustapic L, Delbianco A, Graziosi I, Camilleri, M and Vos S, 2022. Report on 2021 plant pest survey activities. Plant Health and Pesticide Residues (PLANTS) Unit, Plant Health Monitoring team. European Food Safety Authority. 5 pp. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6323563

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Table 1: Outputs on plant pest surveillance published in 2021

Outputs		Publication date	Mandate number	Link to the output	
Pest survey cards: what, when, where and how to survey?	Tutorial video	7 April	M-2020-0114	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kHANmRDex8&t=10s	
Index of the Pest Survey Toolkit	Pest Survey Toolkit	14 October	M-2017-0137, M-2020-0014	https://arcg.is/1v99CH	
				EFSA Journal	StoryMap
New Pest survey cards	<i>Anastrepha ludens</i>	29 January	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2021.EN-1998	-
	<i>Bactrocera zonata</i>	29 January	M-2020-0114	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2021.EN-1999	-
	' <i>Candidatus</i> Phytoplasma aurantifolia'-reference strain and its vector <i>Hishimonus phycitis</i>	6 May	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2021.EN-7026	https://arcg.is/19SK8v
	<i>Ceratocystis platani</i>	14 September	M-2020-0114	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2021.EN-6822	https://arcg.is/1GCW4C0
	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>	7 July	M-2017-0137	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1894	https://arcg.is/1DSaau1
	<i>Naupactus leucoloma</i>	29 November	M-2020-0114	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2021.EN-6990	https://arcg.is/110Ga9
	Satsuma dwarf virus	17 November	M-2020-0114	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2021.EN-6941	https://arcg.is/1GCW4C0
Updated Pest survey cards	<i>Anoplophora chinensis</i>	19 May	M-2020-0114	-	https://arcg.is/19HTyn
	<i>Anoplophora glabripennis</i>	19 May	M-2020-0114	-	https://arcg.is/KOCb9
	<i>Aromia bungii</i>	26 January	M-2020-0114	-	https://arcg.is/1r09uO
	' <i>Candidatus</i> Liberibacter solanacearum', its vector <i>Bactericera cockerelli</i> and other insect vectors	4 February	M-2017-0114	-	https://arcg.is/0bqWC8
	<i>Phylosticta citricarpa</i>	22 December	M-2020-0114	-	https://arcg.is/0C0Wr8
	<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>	22 March	M-2020-0114	-	https://arcg.is/1uyi4i
	<i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>	2 July	M-2020-0114	-	https://arcg.is/09m4r1

Table 2: Events which the plant pest surveillance project has organised or been involved with in 2021

Event		Date	Organiser	Participants	Available material
3rd European Conference on <i>Xylella fastidiosa</i> and XF-ACTORS final meeting	EFSA guidelines for risk-based survey design for <i>Xylella fastidiosa</i>	26-30 April	EFSA, XF-ACTORS, BIOVEXO, CURE-XF, ERC MultiX, EUPHRESCO, EUROXANTH, and Life Resilience	Sybren Vos	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2021-06/Vos-Sybren.pdf https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/events/event/3rd-european-conference-xylella-fastidiosa-and-xf-actors-final-meeting
Chief Plant Health Officers (COPHs) meeting	EFSA activities on contingency and surveillance	29-30 April	European Commission	Sybren Vos	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6320685
EC Working Group on Plant Health Surveillance	Statistically-based surveys and innovative approaches for territorial surveillance	17-18 March	European Commission	Antonio Vicent, Elena Lázaro, Giulia Mattion, Ignazio Graziosi, Stephen Parnell, Sybren Vos	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6245213
	Surveillance of quarantine long-horned beetles in the EU	21 May	European Commission	Sybren Vos, Giulia Mattion, Ignazio Graziosi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6011396
EC-EPPO meeting	Toolkit for plant pest surveillance, multi-pest survey protocol: Citrus	08 December	European Commission, European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organisation	Sybren Vos, Jose Cortiñas Abrahantes	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6008893
EFSA sessions	95 th Plant Health Plenary	29-30 September	EFSA	Alice Delbianco, Antonio Vicent, Elena Lázaro, Hans-Hermann Thulke, Juan Navas-Cortes, Luka Mustapic, Sybren Vos	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/events/event/95th-plh-plenary-meeting
	Network meeting	9-10 December	EFSA	Alice Delbianco, Elena Lázaro, Jose Cortiñas Abrahantes, Juan Navas-Cortes, Luka Mustapic, Stephen Parnell, Sybren Vos	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/events/17th-meeting-efsa-scientific-network-risk-assessment-plant-health

Meetings	Using RIBESS+ for <i>Xylella fastidiosa</i> surveys, Regional Plant Protection Service, Apulia region, Italy	10 September	EFSA, NPPO, Apulia	Alice Delbianco, Ignazio Graziosi, Jose Cortiñas Abrahantes, Sybren Vos	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6012033
	Using RIBESS+ for <i>Xylella fastidiosa</i> surveys, Slovenian National Institute of Biology	7 September	EFSA, Slovenian National Institute of Biology	Alice Delbianco, Ignazio Graziosi, Luka Mustapic, Sybren Vos	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6320673
	Using RIBESS+ for <i>Xylella fastidiosa</i> surveys, Regional Plant Protection Service, Tuscany Region	11 March	EFSA, NPPO of Tuscany	Alice Delbianco, Giulia Mattion, Ignazio Graziosi, Sybren Vos,	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6012407
Symposium	IUFRO- International symposium on Pine Wilt Disease	22-26 November	International Union of Forest Research Organizations (IUFRO)	Sybren Vos	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6320632 https://symposium.inrae.fr/pwd2020/
Webinars	Global Action for Fall Armyworm (FAW) control – regional NPPO of Lombardy region	23 March	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) Global Action for FAW control	Giulia Mattion	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6320697
	International Year of Plant Health (IYPH) Webinar on Food Systems and Plant Health	29-30 June	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO)	Sybren Vos	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6320605 https://www.fao.org/plant-health-2020/events/events-detail/en/c/1373526/
Working groups meetings	Pest survey cards review	2021	EFSA	EFSA Working group on Pest Survey cards review	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/wgs/plant-health/wg-plh-Pest-Survey.pdf
	Pest survey methods	2021	EFSA	EFSA Working group on Pest Survey Methods	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/wgs/plant-health/wg-pest-survey-methods-m-2020-0114.pdf

Workshops	2 nd Annual workshop of the EURL for Plant Parasitic Nematodes.	30 November-1 December	European Union Reference Laboratory (EURL) for Plant Parasitic Nematodes	Alice Delbianco	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6320543 https://sitesv2.anses.fr/en/minisite/plant-parasitic-nematodes/2021-workshop-eurl-plant-parasitic-nematodes
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